

School Heads' Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership

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Abstract:

Examining the chemistry between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership is crucial for schools hoping to survive today's complex and ever-changing environment. In this premise, this study analyzed the school heads' emotional intelligence and transformational leadership level in a medium-sized School Division in a fourth-class component city in Central Philippines for School Year 2021-2022. Data needed for this descriptive study was collected from 30 school heads using a self-made data-gathering instrument that has passed stringent validity and reliability tests. The data analysis revealed that school heads exhibited a very high level of emotional intelligence in areas like self-awareness, motivating oneself, empathy, managing emotions, and social skills. School heads also demonstrated a high level of individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, and idealized influence. The findings highlight the importance of school heads emphasizing enhancing emotional intelligence and fostering transformational leadership skills through professional development initiatives while also engaging in collaborative efforts with staff to implement evidence-backed strategies for improving schools.

Keywords: Leadership, emotional intelligence, transformational leadership, very high, school heads, Negros Occidental, Philippines

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

School heads must embody emotional intelligence and transformational leadership qualities to lead educational institutions effectively. This necessitates a deep understanding of how these elements intersect and influence one another to develop positive outcomes within schools (Gómez-Leal et al., 2021).

Despite recognizing the importance of emotional intelligence and transformational leadership in educational leadership, there remains a gap in practice, with some school heads failing to embody these qualities. This disconnect between the recognized standards and the actual leadership exhibited by some individuals underscores the need for further investigation into the barriers preventing the integration of emotional intelligence and transformational leadership in educational leadership (Munir et al., 2023). Consequently, understanding the factors contributing to the absence of these qualities among some school leaders is crucial for addressing the disparities in effective leadership practices within educational institutions.

Current State of Knowledge

Daniel Goleman and Peter Salovey's work has elucidated the components of EI, emphasizing its role in interpersonal relationships and work performance. Similarly, James MacGregor Burns and Bernard M. Bass have contributed to understanding transformational leadership, highlighting its ability to inspire change and foster collaboration within organizations (Fritch, 2020). These concepts have been further explored in studies conducted in the Philippines, such as those by Imperial (2021) and Mangulabnan (2021), which underscore the importance of EI and transformational leadership in enhancing school environments and improving teacher performance.

Furthermore, various studies have investigated the relationships between EI, leadership qualities, and academic performance among educators. Notable contributions include the works of Ocampo (2019) and Saud (2019), which found correlations between high EI levels among school heads and effective emotional management, aligning with findings from other studies emphasizing the impact of EI on leadership effectiveness (Shehhi, 2021). Mason (2018) investigated the role of emotional intelligence in school leadership and found that leaders with higher emotional intelligence tend to foster positive interactions with stakeholders. Similarly, Go et al. (2020) discovered that Filipino teachers with high emotional intelligence displayed better teaching performance, reflecting similarities

with the school heads in this study, who exhibited high levels of empathy. Swift and Charis Lee's (2018) study supported the importance of emotional intelligence, particularly empathy, in teacher job satisfaction. Garcia (2021) highlighted the positive impact of transformational leadership on reducing role ambiguity and promoting work-life balance, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Moreover, investigations into transformational leadership styles have yielded insights into their impacts on organizational climate and employee motivation. A study by Yuan-Duen Lee (2019) emphasizes the importance of transformational leadership in promoting job satisfaction and work motivation among teachers, particularly through individualized consideration and inspirational motivation (Mangulabnan, 2021). Similarly, research by Pagador (2018) and Chollathanrattanapong (2022) highlights the correlations between transformational leadership qualities and positive school climates, fostering environments conducive to teacher motivation and innovation. Additionally, the work of Manongsong (2019) underscores the significance of idealized influence in shaping teachers' perceptions of leadership effectiveness and job satisfaction, further illustrating the impact of transformational leadership on educational outcomes. Gutiérrez-Cobo et al. (2019) revealed a significantly higher total EI for head teachers than for teachers.

Theoretical Underpinnings

Goleman's theory delineates emotional intelligence as skills and competencies encompassing self-awareness, emotional management, motivation, empathy, and social skills. This framework provides insights into the emotional well-being of school leaders, teachers, and students, influencing their decision-making, interpersonal interactions, and overall performance (Defalco, 2019). McGregor Burns' Theory of Transformational Leadership emphasizes leadership as a catalyst for positive change within individuals and social systems, promoting follower development and organizational growth. Transformational leadership is through role modeling, inspiring vision, and individualized consideration (Lea, 2019).

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the school heads' level of emotional intelligence and transformational leadership in a medium-sized School Division in a fourth-class component city in Central Philippines during the School Year 2021-2022. Specifically, this study sought to determine: 1) the level of emotional intelligence of school heads according to self-awareness, managing emotions, motivating oneself, empathy, and social skills; and 2) the level of transformational leadership of school heads according to individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, and idealized influence.

Research Methodology:

The research design is one of the methodology-related components of the investigation. This section describes the respondents, study instrument, data gathering process, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive research design to determine the level of emotional intelligence among school heads, transformational leadership, and school performance. According to Creswell (2023), descriptive research design is a study that describes the characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. They are primarily used to gain an understanding of a group or phenomenon.

Respondents

This paper employed purposive sampling to select participants. The study's respondents consist of school heads from diverse educational institutions, totaling 30 individuals.

Data Collection

The research instrument utilized in this study was researcher-developed and subjected to validity and reliability. The instrument used in this study focuses on evaluating the school heads' emotional intelligence and transformational leadership practices, respectively.

Data Analysis/Statistical Treatment

This study utilized various analytical approaches consistent with the study's research objectives. It used a descriptive-analytical scheme and means as statistical tools to determine the school head's emotional intelligence and transformational leadership.

Ethical Considerations

The participants' rights were ensured, with a focus on maintaining confidentiality and restricting access to their responses solely to the researchers involved. Measures were implemented to prevent participants' identification, including omitting their names from the written report. Clear assurances were given regarding segregating consent forms from data records to uphold confidentiality, with strict compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 observed throughout the study. Participants were assured of the utmost importance of their privacy. They were informed of the measures taken to safeguard their anonymity, with guidelines in place to prevent unauthorized access or disclosure of their information.

Results and Discussion

The data gathered from the respondents' responses were tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis and interpretation following the study's objectives.

Table 1

Level of Emotional Intelligence of School Heads in Self-Awareness

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I realize immediately when I lose my temper.	4.66	Very High Level
2. I know when I am happy.	4.80	Very High Level
3. I usually recognize when I am stressed	4.76	Very High Level
4. When I am being 'emotional,' I am aware of this	4.63	Very High Level
5. When I feel anxious, I usually can account for the reason(s)	4.60	Very High Level
6. I always know when I'm being unreasonable	4.26	Very High Level
7. Awareness of my own emotions is very important to me at all times.	4.66	Very High Level
8. I can tell if someone has upset or annoyed me	4.36	Very High Level
9. I can let anger 'go' quickly so it no longer affects me.	4.43	Very High Level
10. I can suppress my emotions when I need to.	4.46	Very High Level
Mean	4.56	Very High Level

The overall mean score for all the items related to self-awareness is 4.56, indicating a "Very High Level" of emotional intelligence among the school heads in this aspect. A closer look at the individual items shows consistently high mean scores, with all items falling within the "Very High Level" and "High Level" categories. This suggests that the school heads in the study possess a solid ability to recognize and understand their emotions, including both positive and negative ones.

The lowest mean score is associated with Item 6, which states, "I always know when I'm being unreasonable," with a mean score of 4.26, indicating a High Level of self-awareness. This lower score on the specific item implies a potential area for improvement in the school heads' self-awareness, particularly in accurately gauging their behavior for reasonableness. It may indicate a need for increased mindfulness and reflection on their actions to ensure a more consistent awareness of their reasonableness or lack thereof.

The implications of these findings are noteworthy, especially in the context of school leadership. Mason, Tanzy L. (2018) conducted a study on the role of emotional intelligence in the work of school leaders. The results of this current study align with Mason's findings, as they both indicate that school leaders with higher emotional intelligence tend to foster positive interactions with stakeholders.

Furthermore, the study by Cobo (2019) compared the emotional intelligence of head teachers with that of schoolteachers in other positions. This current study's results, with the school heads demonstrating a "Very High Level" of self-awareness, align with Cobo's findings, further supporting the notion that school leaders tend to have higher emotional intelligence than teachers in other roles.

Table 2

Level of Emotional Intelligence of School Heads in Managing Emotions

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I can 'reframe' bad situations quickly.	4.56	Very High Level
2. I do not wear my 'heart on my sleeve.'	4.46	Very High Level
3. Others can rarely tell what kind of mood I am in.	4.30	Very High Level
4. I rarely 'fly off the handle' at other people.	4.30	Very High Level
5. Difficult people do not annoy me.	4.40	Very High Level
6. I can consciously alter my frame of mind or mood	4.43	Very High Level

7.	I do not let stressful situations or people affect me once I have left work.	4.50	Very High Level
8.	I rarely worry about work or life in general.	4.26	Very High Level
9.	I can suppress my emotions when I need to.	4.43	Very High Level
10.	Others often do not know how I am feeling about things.	4.53	Very High Level
Mean		4.42	Very High Level

Table 2 indicates that the school heads possess a very high level of emotional intelligence in certain areas, such as quickly reframing bad situations, not openly displaying their emotions (not wearing their 'heart on their sleeve'), and being able to consciously alter their frame of mind or mood. They also exhibit a very high level of emotional intelligence in other aspects, such as rarely 'flying off the handle' at other people, not letting stressful situations or people affect them once they have left work, and rarely worrying about work or life in general.

The lowest mean score is associated with Item 8, which states, "I rarely worry about work or life in general," with a mean score of 4.26, indicating a Very High Level of Emotional Intelligence. While the overall level of emotional intelligence for the school heads in the area of managing emotions is categorized as Very High (with a mean of 4.42), the relatively lower score on Item 8 suggests that there might be some instances where school heads experience concerns or worries about work or life.

Relating these findings to previous studies, the school heads in this study show similarities with the findings from Ocampo (2019) and Saud (2019). Ocampo (2019) found that Master Teachers exhibited high emotional intelligence in managing their own emotions and others' emotions, which aligns with the high level of emotional intelligence demonstrated by the school heads in this study. Similarly, Saud (2019) found that Saudi EFL undergraduates had high emotional intelligence, particularly in utilizing emotions and managing others' emotions, which also mirrors the high level of emotional intelligence displayed by the school heads.

Table 3

Level of Emotional Intelligence of School Heads in Motivating Oneself

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I can always motivate myself to do complex tasks.	4.53	Very High Level
2. I can usually prioritize important activities at work and get on with them.	4.56	Very High Level
3. I always meet deadlines.	4.56	Very High Level
4. I never waste time.	4.36	Very High Level
5. I do not prevaricate.	4.56	Very High Level
6. I believe you should do the difficult things first.	4.36	Very High Level
7. Delayed gratification is a virtue that I hold to.	4.43	Very High Level
8. I believe in 'Action this Day'.	4.50	Very High Level
9. I can always motivate myself even when I feel low.	4.56	Very High Level
10. Motivation has been the key to my success.	4.60	Very High Level
Mean	4.50	Very High Level

All mean scores are relatively high, indicating a Very High Level (4.50) of emotional intelligence for school heads in motivating themselves. However, the lowest mean score is associated with Item 4, which states, "I never waste time," with a mean score of 4.36, still reflecting a High Level of emotional intelligence. While the overall level of emotional intelligence in motivating oneself is exemplary, the slightly lower score on Item 4 suggests that there may be occasional instances where school heads perceive some time being utilized less efficiently.

The findings suggest that school heads possess a very high level of emotional intelligence regarding self-motivation. They consistently demonstrate the ability to motivate themselves to undertake complex tasks and prioritize essential activities at work, as evidenced by the high mean scores for items such as always motivating themselves to do complex tasks, meeting deadlines, and believing in "Action this Day."

Furthermore, the school heads' high level of emotional intelligence is evident in their ability to remain motivated even when they feel low. The high mean score for the item "I can always motivate myself even when I feel low" suggests that they have developed resilience and the capacity to stay motivated during challenging times, which can be crucial for effective leadership.

The implications of this high level of emotional intelligence in motivating oneself are significant for the effectiveness of the school heads' leadership. Motivation is a critical aspect of leadership, and leaders who can consistently motivate themselves are better equipped to inspire and motivate their teams, creating a positive and productive work environment.

The findings from Shehhi (2021) align with the notion that emotional intelligence enables principals to build relationships and establish trust to improve their schools. The high level of emotional intelligence in motivating oneself may translate to better interpersonal relationships and communication skills, which can foster positive relationships with teachers, staff, and students.

Table 4
Level of Emotional Intelligence of School Heads in Empathy

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I am always able to see things from the other person's viewpoint.	4.63	Very High Level
2. I am excellent at empathizing with someone else's problem.	4.63	Very High Level
3. I can tell if someone is not happy with me.	4.56	Very High Level
4. I can tell if a team of people is not getting along with each other.	4.56	Very High Level
5. I can understand why people are having difficulties with me.	4.56	Very High Level
6. Other individuals are not 'difficult'; they are just 'different.'	4.66	Very High Level
7. I can understand if I am being unreasonable.	4.63	Very High Level
8. I can understand why my actions sometimes offend others.	4.70	Very High Level
9. I can see things from others' points of view.	4.76	Very High Level
10. Reasons for disagreements are always clear to me.	4.73	Very High Level
Mean	4.64	Very High Level

All mean scores are notably high, indicating a Very High Level (4.64) of emotional intelligence for school heads in empathy. However, the lowest mean score is associated with Item 5, which states, "I can usually understand why people are being difficult towards me," with a mean score of 4.56, still reflecting a Very High Level of emotional intelligence.

The findings reveal that the school heads possess a very high level of empathy. They consistently demonstrate the ability to see things from the other person's viewpoint, empathize with someone else's problems, and understand if someone is unhappy with them. Additionally, they display a high level of understanding and sensitivity towards team dynamics, being able to tell if a team of people is not getting along with each other. They also exhibit empathy in challenging situations, understanding why people may be difficult towards them and acknowledging that other individuals are not 'difficult' but 'different.'

The implications of this high level of empathy among school heads are significant for their leadership effectiveness and school climate. Leaders with a strong sense of empathy are likelier to foster a supportive and caring environment, promoting better communication, collaboration, and teamwork.

The school heads in this study share similarities with the conclusions drawn from the study conducted by Go et al. (2020). Go et al. found that Filipino teachers displayed high emotional intelligence and the ability to compartmentalize their problems, which positively correlated with their teaching performance. Additionally, the study by Swift and Charis Lee (2018) supports the importance of emotional intelligence, particularly empathy, in the context of teacher job satisfaction. The strong relationship between teacher's perceptions of their principal's emotional intelligence and the teachers' level of job satisfaction indicates that empathetic school leadership can significantly impact the overall satisfaction and well-being of teachers within the school.

Table 5
Level of Emotional Intelligence of School Heads in Social Skill

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I am an excellent listener.	4.50	Very High Level
2. I never interrupt other people's conversations.	4.43	Very High Level
3. I am good at adapting and mixing with a variety of people.	4.46	Very High Level
4. People are the most exciting thing in life for me.	4.43	Very High Level
5. I love meeting new people and learning what makes them 'tick.'	4.50	Very High Level
6. I need a variety of work colleagues to make my job enjoyable.	4.56	Very High Level
7. I like to ask questions to find out what is important to people.	4.53	Very High Level
8. Working with difficult people is simply a challenge to win them over.	4.53	Very High Level
9. I am good at reconciling differences with other people.	4.43	Very High Level
10. I generally build solid relationships with those I work with.	4.50	Very High Level
Mean	4.49	Very High Level

All mean scores are quite high, indicating a generally Very High Level (4.49) of emotional intelligence for school heads in social skills. However, the lowest mean score is associated with Item 2, which states, "I never interrupt other people's conversations," with a mean score of 4.43, still reflecting a Very High Level of social skill. While the overall level of social skill is commendable, the slightly lower score on Item 2 suggests that there may be instances where school heads might interrupt conversations, albeit infrequently. This lower score implies a potential area for refinement in communication etiquette for some school heads.

The findings reveal that the school heads possess high social skills, including effective listening, respecting others' conversations, adapting well to different people, and genuinely valuing interactions with others.

Furthermore, the school heads demonstrate a high level of skill in building and maintaining solid relationships with their colleagues. They approach working with difficult people as a challenge to overcome.

The implications of this high level of social skills among school heads are significant for their leadership effectiveness and the overall school climate. Leaders with strong social skills are better equipped to foster a positive and supportive work environment, leading to improved team dynamics, communication, and collaboration.

Table 6
Level of Transformational Leadership of School Heads in Individualized Consideration

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Giving praise and appreciation to the work results or achievements of teachers.	4.56	Very High Level
2. Accepting suggestions for their improvements.	4.63	Very High Level
3. Routinely giving particular time to teachers to deliver every opinion.	4.63	Very High Level
4. Asking for the opinion regarding the leadership in higher education.	4.66	Very High Level
5. Carrying out or following up on the suggestions submitted.	4.66	Very High Level
6. Telling teachers to check the evaluation results to make up for any shortcomings.	4.56	Very High Level
7. Carrying out an informal approach.	4.53	Very High Level
8. Guiding and training teachers personally if they have problems.	4.60	Very High Level
9. Knowing the skills or expertise of teachers.	4.70	Very High Level
10. Knowing the needs of teachers for the flow of the teaching and learning activities in the classroom.	4.73	Very High Level
11. Giving attention by listening to the complaints of teachers for mutual comfort.	4.70	Very High Level
Mean	4.63	Very High Level

All mean scores are exceptionally high, indicating a Very High Level of transformational leadership for school heads in individualized consideration. However, it is important to note that there are no low scores in this table, as all items reflect a Very High Level of leadership behavior. The lowest mean score in this table is associated with Item 7, which states, "Carrying out an informal approach," with a mean score of 4.53. Although this score still falls within the Very High-Level category, the slightly lower score suggests that school heads may engage in informal approaches with teachers slightly less frequently than other aspects of individualized consideration. This lower score implies a potential area for school heads to explore and incorporate more informal approaches in their leadership style.

The findings reveal that the school heads exhibit a very high level of individualized consideration towards their teachers. They consistently demonstrate practices such as giving praise and appreciation for teachers' work results or achievements, accepting suggestions for improvement, and routinely giving special time to teachers to express their opinions.

The school heads also display a very high level of personal guidance and support towards their teachers. They engage in practices such as guiding and training teachers personally when they face challenges, understanding and recognizing the skills and expertise of teachers, and being aware of teachers' needs to ensure smooth classroom teaching and learning activities.

Relating these findings to previous studies, the study by Duen Lee (2019) further supports the positive correlation between transformational leadership and teachers' work motivation, with individualized consideration being a particularly influential factor. The very high level of individualized consideration demonstrated by the school heads in this study will likely positively impact teachers' motivation and overall work satisfaction.

Table 7
Level of Transformational Leadership of School Heads in Intellectual Stimulation

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Giving books or other references to teachers is a reference for the self-development of teachers.	4.43	High Level
2. Providing opportunities for teachers to conduct education and training.	4.76	Very High Level
3. Providing freedom of opinion for teachers regarding policies in higher education.	4.66	Very High Level
4. Involving teachers in assessing the activities in higher education.	4.60	Very High Level
5. The school head has a way of solving complex problems.	4.70	Very High Level
Mean	4.63	Very High Level

All mean scores are notably high, indicating a Very High Level of transformational leadership for school heads in the area of intellectual stimulation. However, the lowest mean score is associated with Item 1, which states, "Giving books or other references to teachers as a reference in the self-development of teachers," with a mean score of 4.43, reflecting a High Level of leadership behavior. While the overall level of intellectual stimulation is commendable, the slightly lower score on Item 1 suggests that there may be room for improvement in the aspect of providing reference materials for teachers' self-development. This lower score implies a potential area for school heads to enhance their support for teachers' self-development through the provision of additional reference materials.

The findings reveal that the school heads exhibit a very high level of intellectual stimulation towards their teachers. They consistently demonstrate practices such as providing books or other references to teachers for self-development and offering opportunities for education and training, both of which empower teachers to enhance their knowledge and skills.

The school heads also display a very high level of problem-solving skills and innovation. The item "The school head has a way of solving complex problems" indicates their ability to address challenges effectively and foster a culture of creativity and forward-thinking within the school community.

The implications of this very high level of intellectual stimulation among school heads are significant for their leadership effectiveness and teacher professional growth. Transformational leadership that emphasizes intellectual stimulation motivates teachers to continuously learn and develop professionally, leading to improved teaching practices and student outcomes.

Puyod (2021) emphasizes the positive effect of transformational leadership on reducing role ambiguity and promoting work-life balance for employees during the COVID-19 pandemic. The very high level of transformational leadership in the area of intellectual stimulation observed among the school heads in this current study aligns with the notion that transformational leadership practices can positively impact employees' well-being and motivation.

Table 8
Level of Transformational Leadership of School Heads in Inspirational Motivation

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Influencing teachers to be optimistic in facing the future.	4.76	Very High Level
2. Giving recognition for the work of teachers in the form of personal praise.	4.83	Very High Level
3. Giving enthusiasm to teachers to carry out their tasks properly.	4.76	Very High Level
4. Supporting teachers to get good results in teaching in the classroom.	4.80	Very High Level
5. Telling the success stories of colleagues to motivate teachers to be successful.	4.80	Very High Level
6. Encouraging teachers to work hard professionally.	4.70	Very High Level
7. Giving enthusiasm to teachers for finding other methods of solving problems regarding teaching and learning activities in the classroom.	4.66	Very High Level
8. Encouraging teachers to practice new approaches in implementing teaching and learning activities.	4.60	Very High Level
9. Communicating the goals that must be achieved by teachers.	4.70	Very High Level
10. Giving appreciation/praise to teachers for completing their work well.	4.76	Very High Level
11. Providing special time for teachers to discuss how to complete assignments properly.	4.80	Very High Level
Mean	4.74	Very High Level

All mean scores are remarkably high, indicating a Very High Level (4.74) of transformational leadership for school heads in the area of inspirational motivation. However, the lowest mean score is associated with Item 8, which states, "Encouraging teachers to practice new approaches in implementing teaching and learning activities," with a mean score of 4.60. While this score still falls within the Very High-Level category, the slightly lower score on Item 8 suggests that there may be a relatively lesser emphasis on encouraging teachers to experiment with new approaches in their teaching practices.

This lower score implies a potential area for enhancement in promoting innovation and creativity within teaching and learning activities. While the mean score remains at a Very High Level, school heads may consider placing increased emphasis on fostering a culture of experimentation and adopting new pedagogical approaches. Encouraging teachers to explore innovative methods can lead to continuous improvement and adaptation in response to evolving educational needs.

The findings reveal that the school heads exhibit a very high level of inspirational motivation towards their teachers. They consistently demonstrate practices such as influencing teachers to be optimistic in facing the future, giving recognition and personal praise for the works of teachers, and providing enthusiasm and support to teachers in carrying out their tasks effectively.

The school heads also display a very high level of goal clarity and communication. They effectively communicate the goals that teachers must achieve, providing a clear direction for the teaching and learning activities in the classroom. Furthermore, they allocate special time for teachers to discuss how to complete assignments properly, fostering a sense of support and guidance.

The implications of this very high level of inspirational motivation among school heads are significant for their leadership effectiveness and teacher motivation. Transformational leadership that emphasizes inspirational motivation can inspire and empower teachers to reach their full potential, leading to increased job satisfaction, engagement, and commitment to their profession.

Mangulabnan (2021) found a high pooled mean for inspirational motivation among school principals in Central Luzon, Philippines, indicating that they frequently, if not always, practice this aspect of transformational leadership. The very high level of inspirational motivation observed among the school heads in this current study aligns with the notion that inspirational motivation is a significant aspect of transformational leadership. The study by Pagador (2018) supports the idea that transformational leadership qualities, including inspirational motivation, have a significant correlation with school climate dimensions perceived by teachers. The very high level of inspirational motivation demonstrated by the school heads in this study implies that they are likely to positively influence the school climate, fostering a motivating and supportive environment for teachers. Additionally, the study by Chollathanrattanapong (2022) highlights the effects of transformational leadership on team innovation in private universities. While transformational leadership directly affected job characteristics, team learning behavior, and innovation culture, it did not directly affect team innovation.

Table 9
Level of Transformational Leadership of School Heads in Idealized Influence

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Carrying out tasks in accordance with the vision and mission.	4.76	Very High Level
2. Formulating the vision and mission of the study program concurrently to develop the insight of teachers.	4.63	Very High Level
3. Reminding teachers to respect each other and fellow teachers.	4.80	Very High Level
4. Providing examples of good behavior in the university environment.	4.70	Very High Level
5. Instilling a high commitment to the teachers towards the vision of the study program.	4.66	Very High Level
6. Reducing penalties for any mistakes is a professional effort.	4.70	Very High Level
7. Giving freedom to teachers to carry out the tasks given.	4.83	Very High Level
Mean	4.72	Very High Level

All mean scores are exceptionally high, indicating a Very High Level (4.72) of transformational leadership for school heads in the area of idealized influence. However, the lowest mean score is associated with Item 2, which states, "Formulating the vision and mission of the study program concurrently to develop the insight of teachers," with a mean score of 4.63. While this score still falls within the Very High Level category, the slightly lower score on Item 2 suggests that there may be a relatively lesser emphasis on involving teachers in the formulation process of the vision and mission of the study program.

This lower score implies a potential area for improvement in collaborative leadership practices related to vision and mission development. While the mean score remains at a Very High Level, school heads may consider

adopting a more inclusive approach by actively involving teachers in the formulation process of the vision and mission. Collaborative engagement in this strategic aspect can enhance the sense of ownership, commitment, and shared understanding among the teaching staff. School heads might initiate workshops, focus groups, or open forums to encourage teacher input and insight into the shaping of the program's overarching goals.

The findings reveal that the school heads exhibit a very high level of idealized influence towards their teachers. They consistently demonstrate practices such as carrying out tasks by the vision and mission of the school, formulating the vision and mission of the study program to develop the insight of teachers, and providing examples of good behavior in the university environment.

The school heads' idealized influence is based on leading by example and aligning their actions with the shared vision and values of the institution. This behavior creates a positive role model for teachers and motivates them to align their actions with the school's vision and mission.

The implications of this very high level of idealized influence among school heads are significant for their leadership effectiveness and teacher commitment. Transformational leadership that emphasizes idealized influence can inspire and influence teachers to embrace the school's vision and values, fostering a strong sense of commitment and dedication to the institution's goals and mission.

Manongsong's (2019) study on transformational leadership styles of public elementary school heads in the Division of Northern Samar found that teachers rated school heads' idealized influence as "excellent." This aligns with the very high level of idealized influence observed among the school heads in this study, indicating that teachers perceive them as positive role models and are influenced by their actions and values.

Conclusion

The evaluation of school heads' emotional intelligence reveals strengths across various domains. Firstly, in terms of self-awareness, school heads generally exhibit a strong capacity to understand and acknowledge their own emotions and behaviors. This fosters effective leadership by promoting an understanding of personal strengths and areas for improvement. Secondly, in managing emotions, school heads demonstrate commendable abilities to navigate and regulate emotions, contributing to a positive leadership approach. Thirdly, their capacity to motivate themselves indicates a robust ability to remain focused and dedicated to tasks and responsibilities. Fourthly, in terms of empathy, school heads show a collective strength in interpersonal understanding and compassion, fostering a supportive environment. Lastly, their proficiency in social skills highlights their ability to navigate interpersonal interactions with tact and respect, contributing to a harmonious and collaborative leadership culture within educational institutions. In terms of individualized consideration, school heads excel in providing personalized attention and support to their team members, fostering a culture of supportive leadership. This indicates a strong emphasis on recognizing and valuing the needs of individuals within the educational institution. Regarding intellectual stimulation, school leaders effectively encourage continuous learning and self-development among their teaching staff, promoting an environment conducive to intellectual growth. This reflects a commitment to fostering a culture of lifelong learning and professional development. Inspirational motivation among school heads is generally strong, although there may be opportunities to further encourage experimentation with innovative teaching methods among the teaching staff. Overall, there is a culture of inspiring and motivating leadership within educational institutions. In terms of idealized influence, school leaders excel in embodying visionary leadership and fostering a shared sense of purpose within the academic community. They serve as positive role models, inspiring others to strive towards a common vision and direction.

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